

IMPROVING THE METHODS FOR THE DIAGNOSIS OF NONARTICULAR PATHOLOGY OF THE TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT

¹Gafforov Sunnatullo Amrulloevich, ²Aliev Navruz Hasanovich

¹Department "Dentistry, Pediatric Dentistry and Orthodontics" Tashkent Institute of Advanced Medical

²Department of Orthopedic Dentistry and Orthodontics Bukhara State Medical Institute

Received: 16 March 2020 Revised and Accepted: 16 June 2020

Abstract – The article presents the results of studying the features of the biomechanics of the lower jaw in patients suffering from pain syndrome of the temporomandibular joint. Improvement of the efficiency of diagnosis and differentiation is presented, impairment of the non-articular nature of the pathology of patients with PSD of TMJ.

Key words: biomechanics of the lower jaw, temporomandibular joint, dysfunctions, pain dysfunction.

I. Introduction

Diseases of the temporomandibular joint (TMJ) are one of the most urgent problems of modern dentistry. This is due, on the one hand, to the incidence of TMJ pathology. [6,11], and on the other hand - the complexity of the diagnosis [4].

The largest group of patients with TMJ is patients with internal disorders, which are defined as a violation of the anatomical and functional relationships between the components of the joint and make up more than 80% of patients with this pathology at a specialized appointment [10]. In addition to these factors in the etiology and pathogenesis of pain dysfunction syndromes (PSD) of TMJs, both occlusal disorders with pathological processes in the DVJ and chewing muscles and psychoemotional disorders are important [1,9,11].

Trigger factors of the pathological process in the joint can be different: tooth extraction and prosthetics, unusual movement l / j or too wide opening of the mouth when eating, yawning and dental treatment. In this case, some intra-articular ligaments fixing the articular disc are stretched; at the same time, patients complain of pain in the joint, ear, temple, headaches, limitation of the range of mobility of the jaw, clicking, crunching or "locking", a feeling of stiffness of the area [2,14]. Often, during the development of PSD, TMJ, a decrease in the height of the lower third of the face due to pathological abrasion of teeth, pathological types of occlusion, etc., plays an important role in the psychological factors of organisms [12,13].

Modern medicine for the diagnosis of disorders of soft tissue elements of the joint is carried out using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), but this method does not always 100% reflect the state and position of the articular disc [15]. Visualization of the TMJ articular disk is possible using ultrasound (ultrasound), but the criteria for the norm of the position and movement of the disk during this study are not developed, as well as the evaluation of the condition of the disk in digital terms, there is no methodology for evaluating the effectiveness of ultrasound treatment. Publications on the combined use of MRI, ultrasound, R-graphy and functional diagnostic tests in domestic and foreign literature are sporadic.

II. Literature review

Visualization of the TMJ articular disk is possible using ultrasound examination (USE), but the criteria for the norm of the position and movement of the disk during this study are not developed, as well as the evaluation of the condition of the disk in digital terms, there is no methodology for evaluating the effectiveness of ultrasound treatment. Publications on the combined use of MRI, ultrasound examination(USE), R-graphy and functional diagnostic tests in domestic and foreign literature are sporadic.

Thus, in case of internal and external disorders of nonparticular TMJ pathology, it is most difficult to diagnose patients with non-guided articular disc displacement, secondary osteoarthritis and dysfunction of neuromuscular syndromes of non-articular nature, therefore the development of new methods for early diagnosis and differential pathology of articular and non-articular nature in case of TMJ is relevant.

The purpose of the study is to improve the efficiency of diagnosis and differentiation of non-articular disorders in the pathology of patients with PSD, TMJ.

To solve the tasks, a survey was conducted of 167 patients with PSD of the TMJ, who are at the dispensary or who have been treated by a specialist dentist, ENT specialist, and neuropathologist in the departments of Orthopedic Dentistry and Orthodontics, Otorhinolaryngology and Neurology of the BukhSMI located in the base children's and adult multidisciplinary hospitals.

III. Analysis

Patients were diagnosed, according to the revealed decrease in the height of the lower third of the face, their number from the total examined was 90 people in the age groups of 40-45 years (16 patients), 46-50 years (25 patients), 51-55 years (42 patients), and 56-60 years old (7 patients); the average age was 48.8 ± 4.43 years; by gender of the examined were: women - 55 people (61%), men - 35 (38%).

Complaints with a displacement of I / j, aesthetically unsatisfactory condition of the lower part of the face, difficulty opening the mouth, frequent headaches, sensations of stuffy ear, emotional lability, anxiety, bad mood, sleep disturbance. In addition, we distributed the examined by education; secondary education 25 people (27%), secondary special 30 people (33%) and higher education 35 people (38%).

When examining patients, somatic and psychological statuses were assessed and the pathological process lasted an average of 2 years, patients were examined according to a certain scheme and began with identifying complaints, collecting a medical history and a medical history of the patient, examining the oral cavity and MFR, and others[3]. To determine the state of occlusion in the children involved in the study, plaster models were taken; the mold was used to evaluate the state of occlusion using generally accepted methods.

The examined were divided into groups according to the type of occlusion and malocclusion in accordance with the classification of Persina L.S. and ICD-10.

The R-th teeth were carried out on a dental apparatus and an orthopantomograph according to the generally accepted method in order to identify pathological processes of hard tissues of teeth, periodontal, periodontal, as well as to plan further orthopedic treatment, the choice of orthopedic design.

In order to analyze the measurements of the articular elements and their ratios, joint tomography was performed with the mouth as open as possible and in the central occlusion position to establish the localization and prevalence of the pathological process in the TMJ and the tissues surrounding the joint.

And the intensity and nature of pain was evaluated on the basis of visual analogue scale (VDP) pain (Puzin M.N. 1997) and MPQ pain questionnaire (McGill Pain Questionnaire) [16,17]. Using the MPQ pain questionnaire - evaluated; 1) the total (in points) ranking pain index (RPI); 2) an indicator for each of the scales that evaluate the sensory (RPIs), affective (RPIa) and evaluative (RPIe) components of pain perception; 3) an indicator of the number of distinguished descriptors on sensory (NDDs), affective (NDDa) and Evaluative (NDDe) scales. The values of the total rank pain index can be in the range from 0 to 78 points (on the RPIs scale - from 0 to 58, RPIa - from 0 to 15, RPIe - from 0 to 5 points), on NDDs - from 0 to 13, NDDa - from 0 to 6, NDDe - from 0 to 1. Moreover, higher rates indicate a greater intensity of pain perception.

In order to study the peripheral innervation of the masticatory muscles, an electromyographic examination was carried out, with the help of which the total interference EMG of the masticatory muscles was recorded on both sides. As a functional stress test, a stress model was simulated with a determination of the duration of the latent period of the chin reflex. The studies were conducted on a Medicor M-400 electromyograph and the total EMG was evaluated in accordance with the criteria developed by Y.S. Yusevich. (1958).

Clinical and psychopathological evaluation of patients was carried out on the basis of a clinical scale (CS) [7]. The examination also included the following tests: Shortened multi-factor personality questionnaire (SMPQ), Beck depression scale, Spielberger anxiety scale, hostility scale (HS), Toronto alexithymia scale (TAS). Patients' Quality of Life (QOL) was evaluated using the Nottingham Health Profile (NHP).

Statistical analysis and data processing was performed on the IBM PC using the statistical software package SPSS 10.0.

According to the results of a neuropsychiatric study, it was shown that in 40-45 year old groups, the Beck depression scale was 4.6 ± 0.09 ; personal anxiety - 2.1 ± 0.16 ; reactive anxiety - 4.9 ± 0.15 ; 46-50 flight groups - 4.2 ± 0.07 ; 2.0 ± 0.1 ; 4.2 ± 0.2 ; -50-55 flight groups 3.8 ± 0.12 ; 1.8 ± 0.3 ; 3.5 ± 0.42 ; - 4.2 ± 0.07 ; 2.0 ± 0.1 ; 4.2 ± 0.2 ; - 56-60 flight groups; 3.2 ± 0.02 ; 1.3 ± 0.1 ; 3.1 ± 0.2 , respectively.

Analysis of changes in QOL indices was also found to worsen a reliably ($p < 0.01$) greater decrease in the total NHP index than in the older group from $42.2 \pm 1, 9$ to $33.6 \pm 3, 6$ points.

Strengthening the intensity of pain or deterioration in patients with PSD of the TMJ, is directly dependent on the growth of age groups.

Also, it was determined by an objective examination with TMJ BSD, which occurred against the background of a decrease in the height of the lower third of the face, high neuropsychiatric stress and deterioration of the quality of life; the most modern and popular biopsychosocial model proposed by Dvorkin et al. (1992) and this concept takes into account that patients have to deal with a biological problem, a psychological problem and social factors.

The patients themselves, who participated in the study, talking about the causes of the development of PSD of the TMJ, called the performed prosthetics, malocclusion, sudden loss of a large number of chewing teeth, and trauma of the MFR.

Some patients even cited reasons such as frequently occurring inflammatory diseases of the periodontium and oral mucosa (MMOC), difficult extraction of chewing teeth (table 1). Other patients emphasized that the symptoms of the disease appeared after dental treatment, both orthopedic and therapeutic. Some patients, on the contrary, indicated that the symptoms of the disease began to appear as a result of untimely, for one reason or another, treatment by them for dental care.

It should be noted that none of the patients independently identified psychological stress as the cause or initiating factor that contributed to the occurrence of TMJ PSD. The presence of chronic stress was already detected during the collection of a medical history or medical history.

Table №1.
The reasons why patients associated with the occurrence of TMJ pain dysfunction syndrome

The reasons	Amount sick (absolute)	%
Prosthetics	33	36
Malocclusion	7	0,7
Chewing tooth loss	30	33
Maxillofacial injury	3	3
Traumatic tooth extraction	6	7
Inflammatory Periodontal Disease and MMOC	7	7,3
Dental therapeutic treatment	4	4
TOTAL:	90	100

As can be seen from the table, patients most often associated the occurrence of the disorder with the loss of masticatory teeth and prosthetics.

Dental examination of patients revealed: abnormal abrasion of hard tooth tissue (80%), caries (90%), complicated caries (56%), inflammatory periodontal diseases (70.6%), periodontal disease (13%), MMOC diseases (12%), orthopedic structures that do not meet the requirements (62%), halitosis (46%), which indicates a certain role of local factors, as well as the fact that patients did not regularly seek dental care.

As already mentioned, during the collection of anamnesis, the overwhelming majority of patients revealed a stress factor. Dissatisfaction with social and living conditions, as well as the appearance of the dentition, lower face, leads to the fact that patients become irritable, anxious, unsure of themselves, in the success of further dental treatment. All this prevents the dentist from conducting diagnostic and therapeutic measures. It is necessary to take into account the fact that the process of treating a declining bite is not limited to a few visits to the dentist. Treatment often lasts for months.

Patients with a more labile psyche are more difficult to adapt to temporary orthopedic structures, removable prosthetics. In order to form ideas about the role of psychological factors in the development of PSD TMJ, the structure of psycho-traumatic situations preceding or accompanying the development of PSD TMJ was analyzed: Information about the presence of psycho-traumatic situations that preceded or accompanied the development of PSD TMJ: a traumatic situation in the family of 18; change in social status in 7; change in life stereotype in 3; chronic psychological trauma in 10; conflictual relations in the family at 6; conflict situation at work at 19; lack of cash at 18; problems with children in 9 people were noted.

The results show that most of the patients included in the study most often complained of the presence of any chronic traumatic situation with which the patient was forced to put up with, despite an internal protest. Most often, stressful factors such as material difficulties, the threat of family breakdown, job dissatisfaction or the inability to find a decent job were noted.

Thus, in most cases with PSD TMJ, there are fixed combinations of various factors complementing each other, both dental and psychological.

When analyzing the clinical picture and pathological processes in patients with PSD of the TMJ - 75%, accompanied by a decrease in the height of the lower third of the face, the patients complained of pain, crunching, clicking in the TMJ, which appear at the beginning of the opening of the mouth, during lateral movements n / h, with half-open mouth, at the time of closing the mouth, at the time of complete closure of the dentition; for displacement of the jaws or partial blocking during movements in the joint, unsatisfactory appearance of the lower third of the face or dentition, fatigue in the TMJ after chewing: pain in the TMJ area -78%; crunch in the TMJ - 82%; TMJ click - 65%; unsatisfactory aesthetic appearance of the lower third of the face, dentition - 70%; fatigue in the TMJ after chewing - 46%; difficulty in chewing food - 48%; blocking movements in the TMJ - 35%; tinnitus - 56%; congestion in the ears - 12%; dizziness - 9%:

Crunch was also detected by palpation of the joint through the external auditory meatus and by listening to the joint area with a stethoscope. Clicking was determined by palpation through the skin in front of the tragus of the ear.

Noise symptoms that appear at the time of opening the mouth arise as a result of the mobility of the meniscus of the joint, its bending and rapid alignment with movement; at the beginning of closing the mouth - due to the loss of a strong connection between the meniscus and the condyle, the lack of combination of their movements. The meniscus moves late from the condyle. Then he catches up with a sharp contraction of the lateral pterygoid muscle, moving to its original position on the surface of the condyle. The appearance of crunching and clicking at the moment of complete closure of the dentition is due to the fact that the condyles move through the thickened posterior meniscus.

IV. Discussion

The results on the detailing of the symptoms revealed that they differ in character and intensity: acute pain - 5%; short-term - 24%, local - 80%; constant, dumb - 27; spilled - 7%; with irradiation - 14%; and aching - 62% of cases.

Constant, aching, dull pains are observed with a declining bite, acute, short-term - with irrational prosthetics, with a moving bite; acute, spilled and radiating - with nonsynchronous condyle movements, sharp lateral and distal shifts of the lower jaw with a declining bite.

The mechanism of these complaints is obvious: when the posterior part of the TMJ, rich in blood and lymphatic vessels, is compressed, stagnation occurs, which leads to an increase in intrathimpanic pressure from compression of the Eustachian tube and from a violation of lymphatic drainage from the middle ear.

The next symptom determined clinically was the displacement of the condyles of the joints, and therefore the displacement of l / j. Vertical displacement occurs with generalized increased tooth abrasion, deep traumatic bite; vertical with simultaneous distal shift of the lower jaw - with a deep traumatic bite, lack of distal support; the usual lateral position of the lower jaw - with uneven increased abrasion of the dentition, irrational prosthetics, a moving bite, unilateral condyle deformation.

An analysis of R-studies of the TMJ state revealed that in patients with PSD, a TMJ developing on the background of a decrease in the height of the lower face, the contours of the articular surfaces on R-x are even and smooth, and the condyles are rounded.

Thus, during the present study, no organic disorders in the TMJ were revealed, moreover, comparing the data of R-studies with clinical manifestations, we can conclude that the onset of clinical symptoms is more related not to morphological changes in the joints.

The results of a comprehensive study of the psychological status of patients with TMJ PSD revealed that patients with TMJ PSD detected one or another change. The following were diagnosed: anxious - 20%, depressive - 70%, hypochondriacal - 10% syndromes of varying severity: - In anxiety syndrome, internal tension, irritability and anxiety were noted. Patients, asking the doctor questions about their state of health, clearly wanted a soothing answer. They also had sleep disturbance: restless shallow sleep, inability to fall asleep for a long time: When depressive syndrome was characterized by an oppressed and melancholy mood, sad facial expressions, patients answered the doctor's questions in monosyllables, sometimes they could not hold back tears when talking on exciting topics: When hypochondria syndrome manifested unwarranted concern for their health, overestimation of the severity of their condition. Obsessive-phobic syndrome was characterized by the appearance of obsessive thoughts, ideas, memories, fear, and a desire for obsessive actions.

The intensity of pain in patients with PSD of the TMJ was found to be interconnected with such psychological characteristics as anxiety, increased sensitivity to stressful effects, pessimism, and increased attention to their sensations. Apparently, this combination of psychological characteristics leads to increased sensitivity to existing discomfort in the oral cavity and affect the intensity of PS.

It was revealed that in patients with "depressive", "hypochondriacal" types of SMPQ, the pain intensity was significantly ($p < 0.01$) higher than in patients with an "anxious" profile.

Analysis of the distribution of all patients included in the study, depending on the height of the SMPQ profile, made it possible to distinguish three subgroups: a) with slight psychological maladaptation (in the range of 50-60 T-points) - 63% of patients, b) with moderately pronounced (in the range of 61 -65 T-points) - 25% of patients, c) with severe psychological maladaptation (above 65 T-points) - 12% of patients. A further analysis made it possible to identify the following most common types of SMPQ profiles: 1) "anxious" —17.8% of patients; 2) "disharmonious" - 19.6%; 3) "hyperthymic" -15.5%; 4) "drowned" -14.7% and 5) "depressed" -5.4% of patients.

The study of QOL with PSD of the TMJ revealed a moderate decrease in its total indicator, which, according to the QOL methodology, amounted to 2.9 + 0.35 points. This decrease was mainly due to (table No. 2) a negative perception by patients of the need for treatment and an altered attitude of relatives.

Table №2.
Indicators QOL (M + n in points) of the study patients

QOL Method Scales	All sick (n = 90)
QOL reduction due to:	-1,12+0,05
* the need to be treated	
* various restrictions	-1,06+0,03
* change of attitude	
- close	-1,75+0,12
- friends	-0,4+0,07
* restriction	
- activity at work physical activity daily activities	-1,06+0,17
- in leisure activities	-1,04+0,16
- communication with others	-1,22+0,04
- in nutrition	-0,19+0,06
- smoking	-1,06+0,14
- in intimate life	-0,31+0,24
	-0,22+0,31
	-1,09+0,06
* lowering	
- social status	-1,14+0,14
- income	-1,16+0,14
Total QOL	-3,82+0,32

In the study of pain in patients with PSD, TMJ, the parameters of VDP pain ranged from 12 to 68 points, while in most patients the indicators on a scale ranged between 30-40 points.

The relationship between the intensity of pain and the characteristics of the mental status of patients with PSD of the TMJ has been established. It was revealed that the intensity of pain in patients with PSD of TMJ, developing against the background of a decrease in the height of the lower third of the face, depends on the severity of mental changes: the highest intensity of PS differed in patients with severe psychological maladaptation.

The relationship of the severity of pain with the psychological characteristics of patients is established. Pain perception turned out to be interconnected with an increased level of anxiety, tension, and sensitivity to psychological stressful effects.

Factors affecting the decrease in QOL of patients with PSD of TMJ were revealed: it turned out that it was caused mainly by the negative perception by patients of the need to be treated, to wear removable orthopedic structures in the OC.

QOL was also affected by the intensity of pain and certain psychological characteristics of patients: dissatisfaction, tension, anxiety, rigidity, a sense of injustice and hostility from others, low psychological stress tolerance, and being stuck with negative emotions.

Thus, a wide range of disorders leads to the development of PSD of the TMJ, among which can be distinguished violations from the side of the emergency, muscle system and psychological characteristics.

V. Conclusion

1. A wide range of disorders leads to the development of PPSD of the TMJ, among which can be distinguished violations from the side of the emergency, the muscular apparatus and psychological characteristics; The highest intensity of PSD was in patients with severe psychological maladaptation.

2. The inclusion of the psychosomatic approach in the development of a therapeutic strategy for patients with TMJ PSD, developing against a background of lowering the height of the lower third of the face, helps to increase the effectiveness of treatment, as well as reduce its time, which affects patient compliance and promotes the quality of medical care.

VI. References:

1. Badanin V.V. Occlusal splints are an effective method of orthopedic treatment of functional TMJ disorders. // Institute of Dentistry. - 2003. - No. 3.- p. 26-30.
2. Gafforov S.A., Abdrimov I.S. Medical deontology and psychiatry in dental practice. Educational method. The work was approved by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan on 03/28/14. Tashkent-2014. 46 p.
3. Gafforov S.A., Nazarov O.Zh. Syndromes and symptoms of the temporomandibular joint. Clinic, diagnosis and treatment. Educational method. The work was approved by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 14.03.12. Tashkent 2012. 31 p.

4. Lepilin A.V., Konnov V.V. Functional disorders of the temporomandibular joint // Scientific and Practical Conference dedicated to the 80th anniversary of the Clinical Hospital No. 3 of SarGosMU, "Actual problems of modern medicine": Abstracts. - Saratov, 2006 .-- p. 237-238.
5. Puzin M.N. Pain dysfunction of the temporomandibular joint - M., 2002. -160 p.
6. Petrosov, Yu.A. Diagnosis and orthopedic treatment of diseases of the temporomandibular joint. Krasnodar: Council. Kuban, 2007.304 p.
7. Sargsyan A.E. Medical and psychological approaches to the treatment of patients with pain dysfunction of the maxillary joint. 2014.98 p.
8. Semenova N.D., Kudryava N.V., Zhirulin N.B. Psychological research in dentistry // Dentistry. 1999. - No. 6. - p. 57-64.
9. Sivovol S.I. Treatment of pain dysfunction of the temporomandibular joint // Dental Technologies, - 2005. - No. 1 (20) .- P. 45-50.
10. Sysolyatin P.G. Classification of diseases and injuries of the temporomandibular joint. - M.: Medical book, N. Novgorod: Publishing house NGMA. - 2000. - 79 p.
11. Khvatova, V.A. Clinical Gnatology. - M.: Medicine. 2011.296 p.
12. Abraham E., Rabin A., Mejdani M. Unilateral medial dislocation of the temporomandibular joint // Neuroradiology - 1997. - Aug Vol 39, N 8. P. 602-604.
13. Glaros A.G. Temporomandibular disorders and facial pain: a psychophysiological perspective. // Appl Psychophysiol Biofeedback. 2008 Sep - 33(3) P.161-71.
14. Kafas P., Kafas G., Christofides A., Chiotaki N., Theodoridis M. Chewing ability, mood and sleep are negatively influenced by chronic TMJ pain: preliminary results. Res J Med Sci. 2008 - 2- P.5-6.
15. Landes, C. Sonography of the temporomandibular joint from 60 examinations and comparison with MRI and axiography. //Sonography J Craniomaxillofac Surg.-2000.-Vol.28(6).-P.352-361.
16. Melzack R. The McGill Pain Questionnaire: Key Features and Scoring Methods. Pain 1975; 1: 277-99
17. Scrimshaw, S. V. and Maher, C. (2001) responsiveness of visual analogue and McGill pain pain scales. Journal of Manipulative and Physiological Therapy, 24, 501-504.